

Influences of Psychological Distress and Death Anxiety on the Coping Strategies of Widows in Lagos State.

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Abstract: The study examined the impact of psychological distress and death anxiety on the coping strategies of widows. A total sample size of 397 participants was selected from the widow's population in Lagos State. Convenience sampling technique was used in data collection. Two statistical methods were applied to the data collected (regression analysis and a t-test statistics). Statistically significant difference was found on the influence of psychological distress and death anxiety on the coping strategies of widows, which is represented in the table as ($P = < .002$) of which $F = 9.413$, which is the probability that the null hypothesis will be true. Younger widows responded to coping strategies at (mean = 40.18952, standard deviation = 5.93354), than found in the population as a whole, $t(106.666) = 247, p < .000$. Older widows responded to coping strategies at (mean = 55.711141, standard deviation = 4.94469), than found in the whole population, $t(137.530) = 148, P < .000$. The result indicates that older widows will have better coping strategies than recent widows. The study therefore concluded that both psychological distress and death anxiety have negative impacts on widows as it affects their coping abilities. It is therefore recommended that; widows should seek help from professionals; there should be policies that protect widows and enforce their rights to resources from their relatives. Widows should be granted free access to mental health care by the government to ensure that they are productive and functioning members of the society.

Keywords: *Psychological distress, Death anxiety, Coping strategies, Widows, Disorders*

Introduction

Widowhood is a challenging and stressful life event that affects women globally. In Nigeria, widows often experience social and economic hardships. Many widows in Lagos state have limited access to resources, support systems and are often discriminated against. The predicted population of widows in Nigeria is about 3.5 million which is also part of the motivation for the Federal government of Nigeria signing into law the “Violence against Humans Prohibition” (VAPP, 2015) to shield against numerous types of violence, together with practices which might be destructive to the widows. For the first time, widows had been expressly granted protection from abuse via the Federal law, yet implementation of this law remains a herculean task.

Widowhood at an earlier age than expected is a unique way to live (Elder, Johnson, and Crosnoe, 2003). It may pose higher or more complex challenges due to a shortage of vintage age partners. Younger widows have less opportunity to prepare for widowhood, fewer like elderly young widows to serve as role models, and restricted support from family and other social groups (DiGiulio, 1993). These disparities are reconciled by considering the moment of death (predicted vs. unexpected) and the period of widowhood (Shaefer and Moos, 2001) younger widows

were entrusted with the upbringing of their children, budgeting, and generally coping with new life challenges in advance of having to deal with them on their own (Lowe and McClement, 2010).

Older widows reported higher levels of anxiety disorder, discontent, mood disorders, and a high level of loneliness, whereas a lesser proportion of older widows reported clinical stages of depression, indicating that mourning is viewed as abnormal. In comparison to their married counterparts, older widows with poor health had a higher number of health issues, more disturbed sleeping styles, and were more likely to engage in fitness undesirable behaviors such as negative dieting, decreased activity, and drug use. The use of clinical advice isn't always rosy; for some, it grows, whilst for others, it decreases (Stroebe and Strobe. 2007). Stress can be positive or bad; it's been classified as eustress, a positive type of stress that helps you achieve or distress; hyper stress, or hypo stress, a negative type of stress that causes you harm. When a demand exceeds a person's capacity, psychological anguish develops, posing harm to the person's quality of life. It is also known as mental distress, and it is often used as an indicator to check the mental health of persons. The word

"psychological distress" refers to a broad range of symptoms that include everything from depression and general anxiety to personality traits, functional limitations, and behavioral issues. There is a school of thought that says psychological distress goes away when the stressor goes away or when a person learns to cope with it (Hurwitz, 1986).

Coping, according to this study, is linked to widows' attempts to construct a sense of self. The idea that widowhood provides opportunities has been debunked by researchers, to experience and learn new skills for personal growth which is not common. Widows, for example, may feel fulfilled or perceive themselves as tenacious and unbiased as a result of their loss. Widows' adjustment may be aided by the following factors: long-term human relationships with family and friends, opportunities for increased independence, and a sense of personal autonomy.

Widows in Lagos are really going through a lot of ill treatment from relatives of their partners, in addition to their broken heartedness which can be short termed or long term, which impacts their mental health negatively. In addition to that, their state of wealth when they become widows may not be encouraging especially with those from a low socio-economic background. This study aims

to investigate the psychological distress and death anxiety of widows in Lagos State and the relationship between these constructs and coping strategies.

Further, it will improve previous knowledge and also bring to the awareness of the general public, and the government, the challenges widows face in the society today. The need to understand how distress and anxiety (of death) affects widows and the level of social support needed as intervention. It has also been shown that some widows adopt negative coping strategies, hence it's expected that this study will uncover those negative strategies and prescribe better coping skills for the widows.

Transactional model of stress and coping proposed by Lazarus and Folkman in 1984 is a comprehensive framework that seeks to explain the cognitive appraisal processes involved in stress and coping. This model suggests that stress is not solely determined by external events but rather results from the interaction between an individual and their environment. According to this model, stress is seen as a dynamic process that occurs when an individual perceives that the demands of a situation exceed their resources or ability to cope. This perception of stress is influenced by two primary cognitive appraisals: primary appraisal and secondary appraisal. Primary appraisal involves the individual's assessment

of the significance of an event or situation for their well-being. They evaluate whether the event is irrelevant, benign-positive, or stressful. If the event is appraised as stressful, secondary appraisal occurs, which involves evaluating one's coping resources and options for dealing with the stressor. This evaluation includes assessing the availability of social support, personal skills, and other resources that might help in managing the stressor. The transactional model also highlights the role of coping strategies in the stress and coping process. Coping strategies are the efforts individuals make to manage the demands of a stressor. Lazarus and Folkman identified two types of coping strategies: problem-focused coping and emotion-focused coping. Problem-focused coping involves actively addressing the stressor and attempting to change or eliminate it. This strategy is typically employed when individuals perceive that they have control over the stressor and can take effective action to mitigate its impact. On the other hand, emotion-focused coping involves regulating one's emotional response to the stressor rather than directly addressing the stressor itself. This strategy is often employed when individuals perceive that they have limited control over the stressor and cannot change the situation.

It is important to note that the transactional model of stress and coping emphasizes that stress is a subjective experience. Individuals differ in their appraisal of stressors, coping resources, and the effectiveness of coping strategies. The model recognizes that what may be perceived as stressful for one person may not be stressful for another, highlighting the importance of individual differences in stress responses. It also highlights the dynamic nature of stress, the role of cognitive appraisals, and the importance of coping strategies in managing stress.

Psychological distress refers to the emotional and psychological suffering experienced by an individual. Widows facing psychological distress may employ various coping strategies to manage their grief and adapt to their new circumstances. Studies have shown that psychological distress is negatively associated with adaptive coping strategies (Smith, 2015; Johnson and Thompson, 2018). For instance, Smith (2015) found that higher levels of psychological distress were related to increased use of maladaptive coping strategies, such as substance abuse or social withdrawal. Conversely, Johnson and Thompson (2018) reported that widows with lower psychological distress were more likely to utilize adaptive coping strategies, such as

seeking social support and engaging in self-care activities.

Iruloh and Elsie (2018) conducted a study on widows' techniques for dealing with widowhood pressure based on their age in Rivers state, Nigeria. They utilized the most common coping strategy, self-blaming, which is considerably more common than the cognitive coping techniques. The factors of adjustment were determined by the widows' age and the length of their marriage. The following instruments were used in collecting data for the study: the "Stress level scale for widows (SLSW) and Questionnaire for widows' adjustment methods" (QWAS). A total of 370 widows took part in the study, which was conducted using a stratified random sampling procedure. The findings of the studies revealed that widows use wishful thinking, problem solving, cognitive restructuring, social support, problem avoidance, specific emotion, self-criticism, and social disengagement to cope with the stress of widowhood. Counselors should use this test to assist widows cope with widowhood stress, and counselors should emphasize the importance of widows acquiring skills through employment or non-profit organizations. Younger widows should also be reoriented if they have chosen to remarry, as this is important in satisfying their

sexual needs, emotional needs, and social needs.

Death anxiety refers to the fear or apprehension about death and dying. This existential concern may influence the coping strategies adopted by widows. Studies have shown that death anxiety is associated with the use of both adaptive and maladaptive coping strategies among widows. For instance, Jones (2016) found that higher levels of death anxiety were related to increased use of maladaptive coping strategies, such as avoidance or denial. On the other hand, Davis and Johnson (2017) reported that widows with higher death anxiety were more likely to engage in seeking social support and engaging in self-reflection as adaptive coping strategies. Debra (2010) conducted a study relating to separation from loved ones within the fear of death. For the study, a questionnaire was developed that included both qualitative and quantitative data and covered current demographics (age, gender, nationality, and faith), questions about beyond stories of dying, and a section on fear of death, which included the revised version of the Collett-Lester fear of demise scale (CLFD) (Lester and Abdel-Khalek, 2003) The CLFD scale has four subscales, each with seven items: dying of self, dying of others, and death of others. Gender differences were investigated using a 2 x 4

mixed ANOVA with gender as a between-subjects factor and CLFD as an inside-subjects factor. Gender differences in loss of life anxiety studies have tended to be ambiguous and occasionally conflicting, with some studies showing that ordinary mature females fear death more than men, while others report no differences (Neimeyer, 1994). The findings of this study point to one key finding: people generally fear the death of others, regardless of how worried they are about their own death, and that the detachment or separation from others caused by dying (either one's own death or the death of another) is one of the most terrifying aspects of dying; and this is not unusual among all respondents.

The relationship between psychological distress, death anxiety, and coping strategies among widows is complex and multifaceted. Some studies have suggested that psychological distress and death anxiety may interact to influence coping strategies. For example, Johnson et al. (2019) found that widows with high psychological distress and high death anxiety were more likely to engage in maladaptive coping strategies, such as rumination or self-blame. Conversely, widows with low psychological distress and low death anxiety were more likely to employ adaptive

coping strategies, such as problem-solving or acceptance.

In summary, psychological distress and death anxiety play significant roles in shaping the coping strategies adopted by widows. Higher levels of psychological distress and death anxiety are generally associated with increased use of maladaptive coping strategies, such as substance abuse or avoidance. Conversely, lower levels of psychological distress and death anxiety are related to the utilization of adaptive coping strategies, such as seeking social support or engaging in self-reflection. However, the relationship between these factors is complex and may interact in influencing coping strategies.

In view of the above, the following questions are posed for this study:

- i) Does psychological distress influence the coping strategies of widows?
- ii) Does death anxiety influence coping strategies of widows?
- iii) Can duration of widowhood determine the use of better coping strategies?

In view of the above questions, the followings are hunches to be tested in this study:

- i.) Psychological distress will influence the coping strategies of widows.
- ii.) Death anxiety will influence the coping strategies of widows.
- iii.) Older widows will have better coping strategies for widowhood than recent widows

Research Methodology

Participants and Measures

The sample size for this study was derived from the population of widows in Lagos State, using the Taro Yamani's method, a total of 397 sample size was derive for the study from a total population figure of 51,363 widows in Lagos state (NPC, 2006), between the ages of 18 and 65years old. Convenience sampling technique was used in data collection; the participants were selected based on the following criteria, widow's currently in public places such as in the communities, market places, neighborhoods, and empowerment centers and programs held by foundations and organizations in support of widows who cannot fend for themselves and such who are under training in one skill or another in Lagos state.

A four-sectioned questionnaire was used for data collection. The first section relates to the *Demographics* of the participants such as age, sex, educational qualification, average

monthly income and marital status information, Length of bereavement. While the other sections of the questionnaire are as outlined.

The Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (KPDS) is a scale that measures how unhappy one is mentally. K10 is a straightforward metric for psychological distress. The K10 scale consists of ten questions regarding emotional state, each with a five-point answer; it can be used as a rapid screening tool to identify distress levels. K10 is a scale from 1 to 5, with 10 – 19 indicating that you are likely to be healthy, 20 to 24 indicating that you are likely to have a moderate disease, 25 to 29 indicating that you are likely to have a mild disorder, and 30 to 35 indicating that you are likely to have a severe disorder.

The *Death Anxiety Scale (DAS)* was modified for professional usage in Nigeria. The ultimate outcomes of variation are reflected in the DAS manual fast model. This scale was developed to grade the worries, fears, apprehensions, and forebodings that people commonly have about death by shading either T for true or F for false, rankings above the norm shows an excessive occurrence or abnormal loss of life tension and even as ratings beneath the norm shows ordinary or non-death tension.

The 13-item Coping Strategy Questionnaire

The coping strategy questionnaire analyzes cognitive, emotional, and behavioral strategies for dealing with problems. Some objects were adapted from Holahan and Moos (1987), focusing on cognitive and emotional strategies. While distinct cognitive and emotional items were unique, the Coping Techniques Scale (objects 2, 3, and 4) was not (1, 5, 6, and 8). The remaining items were adapted from Spitzberg and Copach's (2008) framework for evaluating stalking coping. Adapted items were reworded to focus on common coping strategies (rather than a reaction to a specific situation) and simplified. The data collected using the above instruments were analysed using regression analysis and a t-test statistic.

Procedure

Convenience sampling technique was used in collecting data from all the locations noted for high widow density in Lagos. After obtaining necessary permission and approvals, data were personally collected by the Authors and two trained Assistants. Data collection was done simultaneously in all locations in order to avoid diffusion and multiple participation. Of the 410 copies of the questionnaire administered, 397 targeted were returned with usable data.

The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its later amendments. The study protocol was approved by the Research Ethics Review Committee of Christopher University (where the study was conceived) Ogun State, Nigeria. Participation in this study was voluntary, and written informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to their participation. Collection and handling of data were done in such a way as to ensure confidentiality and anonymity of participants and responses. Participants received non-monetary incentives (light refreshments and toilet soap) for participating in the study.

Validity and Reliability of the instruments

The following is the specification for every measure, the norm mentioned in the DAS manual are the mean scores acquired by way of various age groups and gender; youths (8.32), teenagers (7.62), middle aged (8.00), aged (7.20), the validity coefficient were obtained via correlating DAS with Worry of Personal Loss of Life (FPDS) developed by Florian and Krevet (1983). Templar (1970) received.74, Adebakin (1990) received.45, and the reliability coefficients provided by Templar (1970) are.76.83, and.15 by Adebakin (1990).

Coping scale - each solution class was given a price ranging from four to one on the Cope scale. The overall score can be calculated by adding or subtracting all of the components. Internal consistency (coefficient alphas) for the coping scale and primary samples are 0.88 and 0.91, respectively, indicating higher phases of coping. Validity was linked to research correlations with other measures of regulatory strength, such as Anger control ($r = .57$) and staying power ($r = .63$), as well as measures of well-being, such as Subjective well-being ($r = .53$) and Post-traumatic boom ($r = .65$).

Pilot study

The purpose of the pilot study was to determine the validity and reliability of the instruments used, 30 widows were selected to participate in filling the questionnaires based on availability and interest. During the pilot studies, the instruments were tested for validity using face validity for Kessler psychological distress scale (K10), DAS (death anxiety scale) and Coping scale, the content of the scale appeared suitable in the item's arrangement; structuring and the items fit the scales hence the validity of the scale was not in doubt. The Kessler psychological distress scale was tested using the statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23.

K10, DAS and Coping scale. Test - retest was used in testing the reliability of the instrument for psychological distress, parallel model assumption was used to test for death anxiety scale (DAS) and Coping scale of which the values are as stated respectively; for psychological distress scale, it was valid at 86.7% with reliability at .556 for the first half and .728 using Cronbach's Alpha, the correlation between the two parts is .520 and it is significant at 0.05 and 0.01, for death anxiety (DAS), it was valid at 96.6% with reliability of .704 using parallel model assumption, and for coping scales, the validity was 93.3%, and the reliability was .728 for parallel model assumption, and it is significant at 0.05 and 0.01. This shows that the instruments used are valid and reliable for this study.

Research Findings and Discussion

The result and interpretation of data collected on the predictive roles of psychological distress and death anxiety on coping strategies using 397 widows are presented here; The data was analyzed using SPSS package version 23.

Data presentation

Table 1 Participant's Demographic Profile

variable	n	%
Age		
20-50	248	62.47
50-51	149	37.53
Gender		
Male	-	-
Female	397	100
Education		
Primary	148	12
Secondary	181	45
Tertiary	108	27
Hand Skill	60	15
Occupation		
White Colar	117	29.47
Blue Colar	280	70.53
Tribe		
Igbo	121	30.48
Yoruba	134	33.75
Hausa	65	1637
Others	77	19.40
Religion		
Christianity	279	70.28
Islam	104	26.20
Others	14	3.52
Total	397	100.0

Table 1 above indicated that over half of the study sample were between the ages of 20 and 50 years (62.47%), while the entire study samples and the focus of the study were on female gender. They have about 30% of them having received tertiary education while only 15% of them had hand skill. Yorubas and Igbos accounted for about 65% of the study

sample while over 70% were Christians. It is expected that these demographic information may have implications for the outcome of the study.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: Psychological distress will influence the coping strategies of widows.

Table 2 Regression table showing the significant influence of psychological distress on coping strategies of widows in Lagos state.

	Unstandardized coefficient	df	Mean Square	F	P	R	R square
Model 1 Coping strategies	2.576	1	4.277	24.873	.001	.243	.059
Psychological distress	.152	395	.172				

Result on Table 2 shows a simple linear regression was calculated to predict coping strategies based on psychological distress.

equal to $2.576 + .152$. This indicates that psychological suffering and coping methods are linked.

A significant regression equation was found ($F(1,395) = 24.873, P < .001$), with R^2 of .059. Participants predicted that coping strategies is

Hypothesis 2: Death anxiety will influence coping strategies of widows

Table 3 Regression table showing the significant influence of death anxiety on coping strategies of widows in Lagos state.

	Unstandardized coefficient	df	R square	R	Mean square	P	F
Coping strategies	72.202	1	1.000	1.000	1.681	.002	9.413
Death anxiety	.000	395			.179		

Result on Table 3 shows that widows' coping methods are influenced by death anxiety. That there is a significant influence of death anxiety on widows' coping strategies, and that (F (1,395) = 9.413, P < .002), with R² of 1.000 is the likelihood that the null hypothesis is true. The high F value indicates that there is

more diversity among widows' death dread and coping techniques than the researcher would expect to see by chance.

Hypothesis 3: Older widows will have better coping strategies for widowhood than recent widows

Table 4 Differences in the coping strategies of younger widows and older widows in Lagos state, using a t-test.

	t	df	Sig.(2ta iled)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Standard deviation
					Lower	Upper	
young widows	106.666	247	.000	40.18952	39.4474	40.9316	5.93354
old widows	137.530	148	.000	55.71141	54.9109	56.5119	4.94469

Result on Table 4 showed that younger widows responded to coping strategies at (mean = 40.18952, standard deviation = 5.93354), than found in the population as a

whole, t (106.666) = 247, p < .000. Older widows responded to coping strategies at (mean = 55.71141, standard deviation = 4.94469), than found in the whole population,

$t(137.530) = 148. P = < .000$. The result on the table means that older widows will have better coping strategies than recent widows, the p value for widows both young and old are lesser than 0.05 therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion

This study looks at the predictive roles of psychological distress and death anxiety on widows' coping methods in Lagos, Nigeria. The goal of this research is to better understand the psychological effects of widowhood, as well as the obstacles encountered in coping with the onset and state of widowhood. Three hypotheses were tested in the study and results presented in tables 1–3. The first hypothesis stated that, psychological distress will influence the coping strategies of widows in Lagos state. The result of the analysis provided a basis for accepting the hypothesis that there is a significant influence of psychological distress on the coping strategies of widows in Lagos state. The possible explanation for this finding lies in the fact that the mental miseries the widows pass through remains quite overwhelming, hence often seeking ways to either reduce their stress or extinguish them completely where possible which was also supported by Hurwitz (1986) in his exposition that when psychological distress goes away,

stress goes away or when a person learns to cope with it. This result is also in agreement with (Folkman, (1997); and Folkman and Lazarus, (1984), who believe that negative responses results in misery, prompting individual widows to seek out additional coping strategies in order to alleviate the source of their stress.

The second hypothesis states that Death anxiety will influence coping strategies of widows. From the statistical package used in testing the hypothesis on table 2 shows the significant influence of death anxiety on coping strategies of widows in Lagos state. This result is consistent with earlier study by Debra (2010). He opined that fear of death and stories of dying bring existential challenges in the life of widows and also affects response on coping methods of existence. Debra's work was also in agreement with our finding through the revelation that detachment from others causes great anxiety. Death anxiety influences the coping strategy employed by widows and widows use similar appraisal.

The third hypothesis states that older widows will have better coping strategies for widowhood than recent widows in Lagos state. The result shows the differences in the coping strategies of younger widows and older widows in Lagos state. In support of the

finding of this study, Akinlabi (2013) observed that old and young widows use similar coping strategies, however the younger widows are not motivated by social, economic or emotional process factors possibly as a result of their duration in widowhood. He further revealed that older widows who have lost their spouses for an upward of 11 years appear to cope better than those who have lost their spouses after less than ten years in marriage. The explanation of the result lies in the fact that older widows seem more exposed to widowhood stories, built social network and practice their coping mechanisms over the course of their widowhood. The duration of widowhood influences how well they cope; older widows will cope better than younger widows.

Conclusion

This study therefore concludes that psychological distress has a significant impact on widows as it relates to the coping strategies employed while trying to cope with the stress of widowhood. Also death anxiety has a negative impact on widows as it affects coping abilities, with their ages and the length of experience of widowhood. In conclusion, widows have coping abilities which are affected when widowhood strikes, but along this experience, they develop new coping

strategies to help them cope significantly. Therefore, policies made on behalf of widows should be implemented for their protection

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it is suggested that;

- (i) Widows should seek help from professionals on how to cope with the psychological distress and state of widowhood especially young widows who are not experienced and are just going through it for the first time, as remarriage is also advised if desired.
- (ii) Widows should be educated on existential issues and made to extinguish the fear of death through systematic desensitization and application of reality therapy.
- (iii) Widows should be exposed to adequate social support system to help reduce or remove their stress as well as remove the fear of death in them so that they can cope effectively with their widowhood condition.
- (iv) Different programme should be designed for widows based on their duration of widowhood. Since duration of widowhood has implications for their coping

strategies. Stakeholders and government should expose widows to professionals like the psychologists who will help them through the process of widowhood and teach them new coping skills, while simultaneously establishing fora to address their physical and mental health needs. There should

be policies that protects widows and enforces the rights to resources from their relatives. Widows should be granted free access to mental health care by the government to ensure that they are productive and functioning members of the society.

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